

The reactions (1) and (2) show the hydrolysis of aluminium sulfate leading to the formation of $Al(OH)^{+3}$ which can undergo polymerisation. The reaction (3) is nothing but protonation of a water molecule which in its turn leads to the reaction (4). Brady⁶, Black⁷ are of the opinion that the Al^{+3} formed in reaction (1) can be absorbed on the surface of soil micelle and consequently lead to exchange reaction. From the kinetic standpoint it is expected that an increasing temperature would favour the forward reactions and evidently this is clear from the data in Table 2. It is expected that for each Al^{+3} ion there shall be three exchanged K^+ ion under ideal conditions.

Again a rise in temperature accelerates the rate of exchange reaction leading to more release of K^+ from the soil matrix. It is seen that at 28° the ammonium acetate exchangeable^{9,10} potassium is only 0.57×10^3 ppm whereas after treatment with 21 mg of aluminium sulfate the soil solution contained 3.66×10^3 ppm of potassium. It has been reported that mature tea leaves contain about 1.7% aluminium, so toxic effect due to application of aluminium sulfate is far more remote^{1,9}. However there must be a critical limit upto which we can apply aluminium sulfate so that it will not interfere with uptake of phosphorous by the plant.

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Synthesis of 4-[5-(4-Methyl-2-Phenylthiazolyl)]-2-Thiazolylihydrazones of Different Carbonyl Compounds

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RECENTLY, Sawhney *et al* have reported the synthesis of differently substituted bithiazolyls as potential anti-inflammatory agents¹. As many of these compounds exhibited significant anti-inflammatory activity, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some analogous compounds. So, in continuation of our work on non-steroidal anti-inflammatory and antihelintic agents²⁻⁶, we wish to report in the present communication the synthesis of 4-[5-(4-methyl-2-phenylthiazolyl)]-2-thiazolylihydrazones(I) of different carbonyl compounds with a view to testing their anti-inflammatory activity.

I were synthesised in excellent yields according to the reaction sequence outlined in Scheme 1.

Scheme—1

1. EtOH ;
2. $Br_2/CHCl_3$.
3. $\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \end{matrix} > C = N.NH - \overset{\overset{S}{||}}{C} - NH_2 /_{EtOH}$ & 4. NH_4OH .

1-Acetyl-1-bromoacetone reacted smoothly with phenylthioamide in ethanol to give 5-acetyl-4-methyl-2-phenylthiazole(II)⁷. 5-Bromoacetyl-4-methyl-2-phenylthiazole(III) was obtained in good yield by the bromination of II with bromine in chloroform. III on condensation with different aldehyde and ketone thiosemicarbazones⁸, which were prepared by treating the corresponding carbonyl compounds with thiosemicarbazide in presence of acetic acid, gave respective hydrobromide salts (I. HBr) of the required hydrazones(I). The corresponding free bases(I) could be easily obtained on neutralization of I. HBr with ammonia.

The structures of the final compounds as well as intermediates were confirmed by their elemental analysis and i.r. spectra. All the final compounds(I) absorbed in the region of $3400-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH stretching) and $1620-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH bending) did

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NOTES

not show any absorption in the region of 1750-1650 cm^{-1} (absence of $\text{C}=\text{O}$). Replacement of hydrogen by bromine

resulted in the expected shift of absorption frequency from 1680 cm^{-1} to 1690 cm^{-1} . The m.p.'s of II and III were also found to be identical with those reported earlier⁷.

Selected compounds(I) have been sent for testing their anti-inflammatory activity.

Experimental

All the m.p.'s were taken in open capillaries in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded for nujol mulls with IR-20 Spectrophotometer.

5-Acetyl-4-methyl-2-phenylthiazole(II): It was prepared by treating 1-acetyl-1-bromoacetone with

phenylthioamide using the literature procedure⁷ and crystallized from methanol yield 66% m.p. 68° (lit. m.p. 67°); IR: 1680 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$).

5-Bromoacetyl-4-methyl-2-phenylthiazole(III): It was prepared by the bromination of II with bromine in dry chloroform following the method reported by us² for the bromination of 2-acetyl-1-methylbenzimidazole and crystallized from ethanol, yield 73%; m.p. 115° (lit.⁷ m.p. 116-17°); IR 1690 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$).

General method for the preparation of required hydrazones(I): A solution of aldehyde or ketone thiosemicarbazone⁸ (0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to a solution of III (0.01 mole) in ethanol (30 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux on a steam bath for about an hour. A brown-red crystalline solid separated out in hot solution. The solution of reaction mixture was cooled, collected by filtration, washed with a little ethanol and dried well to give pure I. HBr. This solid was suspended in water, neutralized with dilute ammonia, filtered, washed with water and then crystallized from a suitable solvent to give the required pure crystalline hydrazone(I). Purity of the compounds(I) was checked by tlc using silica gel G as adsorbent. Physical data of I are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF I

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p. ^a °C	Solvent of Crystallization	Yield %
1.	CH ₃	CH ₃	148-49 ^b	D	60
2.	CH ₃	Phenyl	91 (195)	A	63
3.	CH ₃	4-Hydroxy- Phenyl	141 (233-35)	B	67
4.	CH ₃	4-Methoxy- Phenyl	178 (208-09)	B	72
5.	CH ₃	4-Nitro- Phenyl	243 (>250 ^d)	C	83
6.	CH ₃	4-Amino- Phenyl	187-88 ^b	B	61
7.	CH ₃	4-Diethyl- aminophenyl	170 ^b	B	71
8.	H	Phenyl	97 (217 ^d)	A	69
9.	H	4-Hydroxy- Phenyl	142 (206)	B	65
10.	H	4-Methoxy- Phenyl	173 (215-16)	A	77
11.	H	4-Hydroxy- 2-methoxy- phenyl	122	B	70

a. The figures in bracket represent the melting points of hydrobromides (I. HBr)

b. The hydrobromides of these compounds could not be isolated.

c. Compounds melted with decomposition.

A: Ethanol, B: Toluene, C: Xylene, D: Dioxan/water.

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